

Thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 3-*N*-Substituted-thioureido-2-methyl-6-phenylthieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4(3*H*)-ones

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Thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines¹ and thioureas² possess various biological activities. In order to synthesise physiologically active compounds we have undertaken the preparation of some substituted-thieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines (2a-o) having thioureido group by condensing different aryl isothiocyanates with 2-methyl-3-*N*-amino-6-phenylthieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4(3*H*)-one (1).

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| 2a; R = C ₆ H ₅ | 2i; R = 3,5-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ |
| b; R = CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ | j; R = 2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| c; R = 4-ClC ₆ H ₄ | k; R = 3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| d; R = 4-Cl, 2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₃ | l; R = 4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| e; R = 2,5-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ | m; R = 2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| f; R = 2,4-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ | n; R = 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| g; R = 2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ | o; R = 4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| h; R = 3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ | |

Compounds 2a-o were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity *in vitro* against bacteria *B. megaterium*, *S. citreus*, *E. coli* and *S. typhosa* employing the cup-plate method³ at a concentration of 50 μg ml⁻¹ using DMF as solvent. Known antibiotics like chloramphenicol, ampicillin, norfloxacin and griseofulvin were used for comparison. Compounds 2a, c and i showed moderate activity (14–15 mm) against *B. megaterium* and *S. typhosa* respectively. Compounds 2a, e and k (23 mm) showed comparable activity against *S. citreus* (ampicillin 24 mm and chloramphenicol 24 mm). Compounds 2b (22 mm) and 2m (22 mm) displayed comparable activity against *E. coli* (ampicillin 17 mm).

Experimental

3-Acetamido-2-carboxy-5-phenylthiophene⁴: A mixture of 5-phenyl-3-amino-2-carboxythiophene (5 g), acetic anhydride (10 ml) and zinc dust (1 g) was stirred and warmed on a water-bath. when the solid dissolved after 10 min. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, 76%, m.p. 110°.

2-Methyl-3-*N*-amino-6-phenylthieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4(3*H*)-one (1): A mixture of 3-acetamido-2-carboxy-5-phenylthiophene (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80% 10 ml) was refluxed in ethanol (15 ml) for 1 h. It was then cooled to yield the product (68%), m.p. 221° (Found C, 60.58; H, 4.16; N, 16.20; S, 12.24. C₁₃H₁₁N₃OS requires C, 60.70; H, 4.28; N, 16.34; S, 12.45%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3400–3200 (NH₂), 1678 (C=O), 1580 cm⁻¹ (C=N); m/z 257 (BP) 242, 227, 226, 216, 218, 188, 172, 161, 121, 79, 57.

3-*N*-Substituted-thioureido-(2)-methyl-6-phenylthieno[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-4(3*H*)-ones (2): An ethanolic solution of 1 (2.57 g, 0.01 mol) and 3,4-dimethylphenyl isothiocyanate (1.63 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h. The contents were then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (67%), m.p. 198° (Found C, 62.82; H, 4.58; N, 13.14; S, 15.20. C₂₂H₂₀N₄OS₂ requires: C, 62.85; H, 4.76; N, 13.33; S, 15.29%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 (NH), 1680 (C=O), 1175 cm⁻¹ (C=S); ν_{max} (DMSO) 2.24 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.67 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1–8.12 (9H, m, ArH), 10.12 (2H, s, NH); m/z 420 292, 242 (BP) 228, 163, 121.

Similarly, other substituted-thioureas (yields 50–71%) were prepared: 2a, m.p. 103°; b, 169°; c, 233°; d, 286°; e, 171°; f, 162°; g, 148°; h, 198°; i, 206°; j, 189°; k, 163°; l, 143°; m, 158°; n, 165°; o, 182°.

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